

BUTTON - A Testbed for WbLS and Cherenkov Technology at Boulby Underground Laboratory

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on behalf of the BUTTON Collaboration

The BUTTON Collaboration

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Funded in the UK by STFC from the UKRI Fund for International Collaboration and the MoD, in the U.S. by National Nuclear Security Administration (NNSA).

What is BUTTON?

- **Boulby Underground Technology Testbed for Observing Neutrinos**

- Want to test technologies for hybrid neutrino detection via *Cherenkov and Scintillation* light.
- Current iteration is **BUTTON-30**, a 30-tonne hybrid optical detector.

Goals of BUTTON

- Test different fill media:
 - Water, Gd-Water, WbLS, Gd-WbLS
- Advanced photosensor testing
 - LAPPDs, wavelength-shifting plates
- Flexibility in design
 - Test different technologies/calibration methods
- Figuring out how to build larger experiments at [Boulby Underground Lab](#)
 - BUTTON-30 is the largest so far

Boulby Underground Laboratory

- An **underground science laboratory** in an active polyhalite mine in the UK
- Located in Boulby, northeast England
- BUTON is housed at a depth of **1.1km underground**
- Provides **low background radiation** conditions
 - Low radionuclide content in the salt rock surrounding the lab
 - Overburden lessens cosmic ray flux by a factor of 10^6

Inverse Beta Decay

- **Inverse Beta Decay** is the primary mechanism to see neutrino interactions at the MeV energy scale
- Introducing **Gadolinium** helps improve detection by allowing observation of the neutron's interaction
- There is a **delay** between the prompt signal and neutron capture signal that depends on Gd concentration

Positron forms a prompt signal (Cherenkov)

Neutron is captured in Gadolinium

Gammas emitted, can cause more Cherenkov emission by Compton scattering

WbLS

- **Water-Based Liquid Scintillator**
- Can use organic molecules as scintillator material
- Other, wavelength-shifting material prevents self-absorption
- Problem is how to **mix** and spread these materials out in water
- WbLS locks the organic materials in “**micelles**” that allow it to be mixed evenly
- Explore the possibility of combining this with Gd

Image adapted from: UC Davis Neutrino Group – Water based liquid scintillator

Advantages:

- **Increased light yield** from scintillator
- **Less attenuation** than typical LS
- Retain Cherenkov in water for **directional information**

BUTTON Design

- Tank
- PSUP (PMT Support Structure)
- PMTs
- Calibration
- Water System
- Electronics/DAQ

Tank

- 30-tonne
 - 3.6m diameter, 3.2m height
- Watertight
- As light-tight as possible
- Compatibility with Gd-Water and WbLS
 - Marine Grade 316 Stainless Steel
- Insulated for a water temperature of 10°C

PSUP

- PMT Support Structure
- Need a **support structure** for PMTs/Calibration/Everything
- Assembled inside the tank in a **modular** fashion
- Has capacity for advanced photosensors to be installed later

Photomultiplier Tubes

- 96 10-inch Hamamatsu R7081-100 PMTs
- Low radioactivity glass bulbs
- The PMT base is suitable for Gd-water but not for WbLS
- Acrylic housing for compatibility with WbLS + Gd-Water

Calibration

- A number of methods
 - Diffuser + Light ball light source
 - AmBe tagged source
 - AmBe untagged source
- Aim to calibrate the PMT response
- “Cassette” loading design to allow for flexible inputs
 - Possible different future sources
- FLASE (Florida-Livermore Attenuation and Scattering Experiment)

Water System

- Filter out material and bacterial impurities
- Compatibility with Gd-Water and WbLS (with some adjustments)

DAQ/Electronics

- Read out **96 PMT channels**
- Interface with **control systems** and **monitoring**
- Remote control
- Trigger
- Power management

Simulation

- **Ratpac-Two**
 - Geant4+ROOT+CLHEP
+GLG4sim+others
- Model of the experiment with material properties/optical properties
- **Source** simulations
 - Diffuser simulation based on data
- **Background** rates
- **DAQ** simulation
 - Digitisation, triggering

Radioassay and Materials

- Materials selected for both Gd and WbLS compatibility
- Also want **low radiation backgrounds**
- Radioassay conducted in Boulby's **ultra-low background** facilities
 - **BUGS – Boulby UnderGround Screening facility**

Component	Estimated mass [kg]	Assay results [mBq/kg]			Estimated Activity [Bq]		
		²³⁸ U	²³² Th	⁴⁰ K	²³⁸ U	²³² Th	⁴⁰ K
Tank							
Steel	10000	<3.2	<2.5	<9.7	<32.0	<25.0	<97.0
PSUP							
Steel box tubes	680	<0.7	0.5±0.2	<3.1	<0.48	0.34	<2.11
Steel cylinders	320	19±2	<0.7	<8.8	6.08	<0.22	<2.82
Liner							
Polyethylene	3.2	903±10	58±4	1516±66	2.89	0.19	4.85
Zipties	1.5	<14	<8.7	<153	<0.02	<0.01	<0.23
PMT							
Borosilicate glass	96 PMTs 96	Assay results from one PMT			Activity for 96 PMTs		
		1.62 [Bq]	1.05 [Bq]	0.11 [Bq]	155	101	10.7
Encapsulation							
UV acrylic dome	165	70±4	<2.9	61±44	11.5	<0.48	<10.0
Acrylic dome	197	<7.7	<3.9	<34	<1.51	<0.77	<6.69
Steel plates	370	<20	<4.0	<50	<7.42	<1.48	<18.5
M8 bolts	66	<16	21±6	<45	<1.21	1.59	<34.1
Optical gel	114	<6.9	<3.5	<46	<0.79	<0.40	<5.24
Coax cable	9.2	234±19	70±11	720±152	2.14	0.64	6.59
Silica desiccant	10.0	198±4	450±6	670±35	1.99	4.51	6.72

Summary

- **BUTTON-30** aims to test **WbLS** and **Gd-Water** for **neutrino detection** purposes at a larger scale
- **Other technologies** such as **advanced photosensors** and **calibration methods** can be tested
- The experiment is constructed at **Boulby Underground Lab**
- The **tank** and **PMTs** are installed, the **water system** is installed, **electronics** are set up and initial tests are being run
- Aim to start taking data early **2026**